

Yields were corrected to 12% grain moisture.

Coating rice seeds with relatively small amounts of zinc resulted in increased grain yields each year. The mean increase over the 4 years was 1 t/ha, ranging from 0.6 to 1.6 t/ha (see table).

Although yield increases were significant, zinc deficiency symptoms were observed in all plots each year. But the symptoms were less severe and occurred later with zinc seed treatment. The symptoms of zinc deficiency indicate that the seed treatment, although beneficial, did not

supply all the zinc that the plants needed in the Crowley soil. Other zinc sources are being evaluated, along with higher rates of zinc seed coatings, to overcome the deficiency. □

Response of direct-seeded rice to zinc application in Sudan Gezira

George I. Ghobrial, senior rice agronomist, Agricultural Research Corporation, Was Medani, Sudan

Direct-seeded rice in the Sudan Gezira often shows symptoms of zinc deficiency, particularly in early growth stages. Although most symptoms usually disappear soon after continuous flooding begins (5–6 weeks after seeding), the effect of flooding on available zinc in the soil has not been determined. Therefore, to determine the importance of zinc application to rice production (IR298-12-1-1) in the Gezira, an experiment with 5 levels of zinc (0, 2, 4, 6, and 8 kg Zn/ha) was established in 1977 at the Gezira Research Farm. The design was randomized complete block with six replications. At seeding, the zinc,

Effects of zinc level on plant height, grain yield, straw yield, and major components of grain yield of IR298-12-1-1 planted at Gezira Research Station, Sudan.

Zinc level (kg Zn/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Straw yield (kg/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1,000-grain wt (g)
0	83	4,143	6,688	398	75	20.1
2	85	4,333	7,076	387	17	20.2
4	84	4,250	6,688	396	15	20.3
6	85	4,514	7,076	417	77	20.3
8	87	4,662	7,628	398	76	20.3
S.E.	1.17	144	188	13.5	3.2	0.02

as zinc sulfate, was incorporated into the soil (heavy clay with av. pH of 8.5). The effects of zinc level on plant height, straw yield, and major grain yield components were determined.

The experiment showed that Gezira soils are slightly deficient in available zinc (see table). Grain and straw yields increased progressively with level of

applied zinc (P = 0.05). The application of 8 kg Zn/ha increased grain yield by 12% and straw yield by 14%. The increase in grain yield suggests the positive effect on dry matter production of applied zinc, which increased straw yield and grain specific weight. Zinc level had no significant effect on plant height, number of grains per panicle, or number of tillers. □

Production of blue-green algae in the field

S. Kannaiyan, Plant Pathology Laboratory, Paddy Experiment Station, Tirur-602025, Chingleput district, Tamil Nadu, India

Blue-green algae harness solar energy to fix nitrogen. The rice plants use the nitrogen released by the blue-green algae. Thus, a rice field is an efficient nonsymbiotic nitrogen-fixing ecosystem. In submerged rice soils, biological nitrogen fixation is essentially an algal process that contributes 20 to 30 kg N/ha. Mass-scale multiplication of blue-green algae was attempted in a rice field. Soil was well prepared and levelled. The plots (10 × 2 m) were laid out. Superphosphate, lime, carbofuran, and starter culture were applied at three levels (see table).

The water level in the plots was maintained at 10 cm. Superphosphate

and lime were added and mixed well with the water. The plots were inoculated with the starter culture (*Aulosira*, *Anabaena*, *Aphanthece*, *Nostoc*). Finally, carbofuran was applied to control soil insects. The plots were not disturbed.

When daily evaporation was high, the plots were irrigated intermittently. The algae grew rapidly. In about 10 days algae formed a thick mat floating on the water surface. Fifteen days after inoculation the plots were allowed to dry

Mass production of blue-green algae in the field, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Soil-based blue-green algal yield (kg)				Mean algal yield (kg)
	Rep. 1	Rep. 2	Rep. 3	Rep. 4	
Superphosphate : 500 g Lime : 50 g Carbofuran : 100 g Starter culture : 500 g	18.7	19.4	21.2	15.2	18.6
Superphosphate : 1000 g Lime : 100 g Carbofuran : 150 g Starter culture : 1000 g	20.6	18.9	22.1	24.5	21.5
Superphosphate : 1500 g Lime : 150 g Carbofuran : 200 g Starter culture : 1500 g	24.2	25.3	24.6	22.6	24.1